

Optical and mechanical squeezing with coherent feedback control beyond the resolved-sideband regime

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The noise reduction in squeezed states makes them a powerful nonclassical resource in quantum technologies, especially in quantum sensing, and an essential step for the ongoing development of non-Gaussian states. In particular, optical and mechanical squeezing can both be generated when light interacts with a mechanical oscillator. Here we use a linear optical system as a controller and use coherent optical feedback to enhance squeezing in the unresolved-sideband regime of optomechanics. Feedback control is generally profitable for cooling, manipulating, and stabilizing the dynamics of mechanical oscillators; coherent feedback is then notable for its ability to steer a quantum system toward the highest squeezing without measurement, avoiding backaction. We thoroughly maximize optical and conditional mechanical squeezing feasible with state-of-the-art experimental setups and derive the optimal conditions under which quantum squeezing is generated in the system.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Feedback is a way to control a quantum system and steer it toward a desired target state [1–3]. There are two different types of feedback: measurement-based feedback and coherent quantum feedback. Measurement-based feedback uses measurements to purify the system and introduce conditional operations to the system [4–6]. That is, quantum information is converted to classical information and this is then used to exert control on the quantum system. In contrast, coherent quantum feedback only performs deterministic manipulations of subsystems related to the system, and information remains quantum throughout the control loop [4,5,7]. Furthermore, coherent feedback does not depend on measurements. Therefore measurement backaction, decoherence, noise, latency, dispersion, and other imperfections in data processing and optical control are avoided. In general, coherent quantum feedback can outperform measurement-based feedback [4,5,7,8].

For instance, coherent feedback can be more efficient than measurement-based feedback for cooling oscillators with linear interactions and controls [6,9,10]. It has been shown that coherent feedback can outperform measurement-based feedback even with nonlinear interactions and controls, as long as the system-auxiliary interaction Hamiltonian is bounded [7]. Moreover, the measurement-based-feedback scheme is restricted to timescales determined by the measuring device and actuator control based on the filtered state. However, quantum coherent feedback is restricted only by the time delays associated with the quantum signals crossing the loop [1–3].

Over the past few years, optomechanical systems with feedback control have attracted much interest since the interaction between light and mechanical motion has resulted in various applications and fundamental investigations [11–14]. The measurement-based schemes in cavity optomechanics have focused mainly on feedback cooling [15–31] because of the importance of cooling for understanding the fundamental aspects of quantum physics on macroscopic scales and in the applications of mechanical systems in quantum information processing and quantum-limited mechanical sensors. Recently, measurement-based feedback was proposed and experimentally demonstrated to increase the efficiency of optomechanical systems, e.g., enhancing the performance of an optomechanical heat engine [32], force sensing [33], and normal-mode splitting [34]. Continuous quantum measurements combined with feedback have also been proposed to

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generate and detect squeezed states of the oscillator [35,36]. On the other hand, while optically coherent feedback loops have shown potential for enhancing processes such as cooling [4,9,37,38], steady-state squeezing in the *resolved-sideband regime* [39], entanglement [38–40], optomechanical nonlinearity [41], and optical-to-mechanical state transfer [39], their applications in certain areas of cavity optomechanics remain relatively unexplored. Specifically, the use of coherent feedback for tasks such as investigating classical nonlinear dynamics, quantum state generation for the mechanical and optical systems, and quantum control has not been thoroughly investigated, which is the focus of our work. Our study delves into the potential of optically coherent feedback loops to amplify key processes such as steady-state squeezing in the *unresolved-sideband regime*.

Coherent photon-phonon interaction in optomechanical systems principally leads to squeezing of the optical and mechanical modes, where the quantum fluctuations of one quadrature component are reduced below the standard quantum limit. Quantum squeezing of light has many applications in sensing and metrology capabilities; for instance, gravitational-wave detectors [42,43] and biomedical applications [44]. Since the first proposal of ponderomotive squeezing [45,46], it has been experimentally observed in various optomechanical setups, such as intracavity cold-atom ensembles [47], membrane-in-the-middle optomechanical systems [48], and optomechanical zipper cavities [49]. On the other hand, squeezing of a macroscopic mechanical oscillator could be relevant to investigating decoherence in quantum systems and realizing ultrasensitive force and motion sensors. Several theoretical schemes have been proposed to generate mechanical squeezing [50–52]. With the use of radiation pressure, the thermal fluctuations of a mechanical resonator have been manipulated to produce a stationary quadrature-squeezed state [53–55]. It has been shown that mechanical squeezing can also be achieved in the *unresolved-sideband regime* through various schemes relying on nonlinearities [56], measurement-based feedback [57], reservoir engineering [58], hybrid atom-optomechanical systems [59] and double-cavity optomechanical systems [60]. Finally, optomechanical entanglement and squeezing can be generated rapidly with the use of properly modulated control pulses [61–66].

Ponderomotive effects from mechanical oscillators are proof of an active nature of optomechanical coupling and a potential source of nonclassical states of light. In this paper, we propose the enhancement of ponderomotive squeezing assisted by coherent feedback in optomechanical systems in the *unresolved-sideband regime* [67,68]. Our scheme requires adjustments of the optical path without needing additional optical cavities or interactions with other quantum systems. The system with feedback can generate optical squeezing (almost 7 dB greater than the

open-loop case) with the use of state-of-the-art optomechanical setups. The coherent feedback loop also increases the squeezing bandwidth of optical squeezing relevant for modern broadband quantum optical processing [69]. For the mechanical state, we cannot suppress noise below the vacuum level with coherent feedback unconditionally. However, we can reduce the thermal-noise level significantly more than in the open-loop scenario. For a particular measurement outcome, the conditional state of the mechanical mode will exhibit squeezing if we properly tune the feedback parameters. Our goal is to investigate the response of the generated squeezing to different control parameters in the system; for example, coherent beam-splitter transmittance, feedback delay time, optomechanical cooperativity, detection angle and frequency, and the number of thermal phonons.

This paper is structured as follows: In Sec. II, we present the system under consideration, i.e., a nanomechanical membrane positioned inside an optical cavity subjected to a quantum feedback loop operating in the *unresolved-sideband regime* of cavity optomechanics. We first present and discuss the classical equations of motion and show how the coherent feedback loop affects the steady state of the system. We then present linearized quantum dynamics around classical steady-state solutions. In Sec. III, we discuss the system dynamics via the linearized Heisenberg-Langevin equation, investigate the system response in the frequency domain, and present the output spectrum. Then we study the conditions where optical squeezing can be generated in the system, and finally we present our numerical calculations of the output quadrature and discuss the effects of the feedback loop on the generated output-light squeezing. In Sec. IV, we turn to the conditional and unconditional mechanical squeezing and show how coherent feedback can enhance mechanical squeezing. Finally, we present our conclusions in Sec. V.

II. THEORETICAL MODEL

A. System specifications

As schematically shown in Fig. 1, the coherent feedback loop comprises a membrane-in-the-middle optomechanical setup and a beam splitter (BS1) with adjustable reflectivity, which gives us a level of dynamic flexibility. The system under consideration operates in the *unresolved-sideband regime* of cavity optomechanics. The membrane vibrations along the cavity axis are coupled to the optical modes via the radiation-pressure interaction. The coherent feedback scheme is implemented by our mixing the output of the cavity, described by the annihilation operator $a_{\text{out},f}$, and coherent input from the laser with the operator a_{in} using a beam splitter (BS1). The system's output, corresponding to the operator a_{out} , is then sent to a homodyne-detection system to measure the general quadrature with phase ϕ relative to the signal.

FIG. 1. The optomechanical system with a coherent feedback loop in the unresolved-sideband regime. Input laser light described by annihilation operator a_{in} is combined with the back-reflected light from the optomechanical cavity in a mode corresponding to the annihilation operator $a_{out,f}$ at coherent beam splitter BS1 with transmittance T . The combined field is delayed by τ , including losses η_f arising from the optical fiber or delay element accompanied by vacuum-noise operator $c_{in}(t)$ and fed back as the input mode described by the operator $a_{in,f}$ to drive the cavity field mode with the operator a that interacts with a mechanical mode with annihilator operator b . The intrinsic losses modeled as loss (denoted by the efficiency η_c) through mirror M2 introduce the noise operator f_{in} . The output operator of the light a_{out} is verified via homodyne detection, which consists of a beam splitter (BS2), two detectors (D1 and D2) and a local oscillator (LO) with phase ϕ relative to the signal.

The nonlinear Hamiltonian that describes the dynamics of the optomechanical system is given by [11,12]

$$H/\hbar = \omega_c a^\dagger a + \Omega b^\dagger b + g_0 a^\dagger a (b + b^\dagger), \quad (1)$$

where ω_c is the frequency of the intracavity optical mode and a is the photon annihilation operator. The mechanical mode with frequency Ω denoted by phonon annihilation operator b is coupled to the optical modes with the single-photon interaction rate g_0 . In a frame rotating with pump laser frequency ω_L , the system Hamiltonian is given by

$$H/\hbar = \Delta_0 a^\dagger a + \omega_m b^\dagger b + g_0 a^\dagger a (b + b^\dagger), \quad (2)$$

where we have introduced the laser detuning $\Delta_0 = \omega_c - \omega_L$ with respect to the cavity mode.

The optomechanical Hamiltonian in Eq. (2) yields the following nonlinear Langevin equations:

$$\dot{a} = -i\Delta_0 a - \kappa a + ig_0 a (b + b^\dagger) + \sqrt{2\kappa} a_{in,t}(t), \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{b} = -i\Omega b - \gamma b + ig_0 a^\dagger a + \sqrt{2\gamma} b_{in}(t), \quad (4)$$

where $a_{in,t}(t)$ is the total optical input of the two-sided cavity given by

$$\sqrt{2\kappa} a_{in,t}(t) = \sqrt{2\kappa_1} a_{in,f}(t) + \sqrt{2\kappa_2} f_{in}(t), \quad (5)$$

where the channels linked with the input mirror M1 (decay rate κ_1) are distinguished from the other loss mechanisms. Overall cavity decay rate $\kappa = \kappa_1 + \kappa_2$ arises because of the

coupling of the coherent input with the rate κ_1 and intrinsic losses, including loss through mirror M2 with coupling rate κ_2 . The fluctuating vacuum electric field coupling to the optical cavity, plus a coherent laser drive and a fraction of the output of the cavity due to the feedback loop, is denoted by the input field $a_{in,f}(t)$. The unwanted decay channel associated with the other loss mechanisms is denoted by $f_{in}(t)$. By defining the coupling efficiency $\eta_c = \kappa_1/\kappa$, we can rewrite Eq. (5) as

$$a_{in,t}(t) = \sqrt{\eta_c} a_{in,f}(t) + \sqrt{1 - \eta_c} f_{in}(t). \quad (6)$$

For the overcoupled cavity $\eta_c \rightarrow 1$, the external coupling κ_1 dominates the cavity losses; therefore, photon absorption or loss via the second mirror can be ignored. Next, we write the input optical noise operator in Eq. (6) as the sum of the transmitted vacuum input noise $a_{in}(t)$ from beam splitter BS1 and two additional terms due to the feedback loop:

$$a_{in,f}(t) = \sqrt{\eta_f} \left[\sqrt{T} a_{in}(t - \tau) - \sqrt{1 - T} a_{out,f}(t - \tau) \right] + \sqrt{1 - \eta_f} c_{in}(t), \quad (7)$$

where T is the transmittance of the beam splitter, τ is the feedback delay time (since the feedback does not act instantaneously), and η_f is the feedback efficiency; see Fig. 1. The extracavity-field fluctuations $a_{out,f}(t)$ are related to the intracavity field by the input-output relation $a_{out,f}(t) = \sqrt{2\kappa_1} a(t) - a_{in,f}(t)$ (see the Appendix for more discussion). The operator $a_{in}(t)$, which denotes the optical input noise, satisfies the commutation relation $[a_{in}(t), a_{in}^\dagger(t)] = \delta(t - t')$ and the second-order correlation $\langle a_{in}(t) a_{in}^\dagger(t') \rangle = \delta(t - t')$. The noise operator $c_{in,f}(t)$ is introduced to include losses in the coherent feedback loop. Correlations analogous to $a_{in}(t)$ will hold for the input fields $c_{in}(t)$ and $f_{in}(t)$. It is worth mentioning that by setting $\{T, \eta_f\} \rightarrow 1$ and $\tau \rightarrow 0$, we recover the no-feedback scenario.

As expressed in Eq. (4), the mechanical mode interacts with a thermal environment at finite temperature with damping rate γ . The zero-mean-value mechanical input noise acting on the mechanical mode satisfies the commutation relation $[b_{in}(t), b_{in}^\dagger(t')] = \delta(t - t')$ and the Markovian correlation function $\langle b_{in}(t) b_{in}^\dagger(t') \rangle = (1 + \bar{n}) \delta(t - t')$, where \bar{n} is the mean number of thermal excitations of the mechanical mode [11].

B. Classical dynamics

We obtain the classical dynamics of the system by taking the expectation values of Eqs. (3) and (4) approximating operator product terms of the form $\langle o(t) o'(t) \rangle$ as $\langle o(t) \rangle \langle o'(t) \rangle$. Note that since we drive the beam splitter with a coherent laser $\langle a_{in}(t) \rangle = \alpha_{in}(t) \neq 0$, but the other

two inputs have zero mean values $\langle f_{\text{in}}(t) \rangle = \langle c_{\text{in}}(t) \rangle = 0$. The semiclassical dynamics of the system is given by the following differential equations:

$$\dot{\alpha}(t) = -i\Delta_0\alpha(t) - \kappa\alpha(t) + 2ig_0\alpha\text{Re}[\beta(t)] + \sqrt{2\kappa\eta_c}\alpha_{\text{in},f}(t), \quad (8)$$

$$\dot{\beta}(t) = -i\Omega\beta(t) - \gamma\beta(t) + ig_0|\alpha(t)|^2, \quad (9)$$

where $\alpha(t) = \langle a(t) \rangle$ is the coherent amplitude in the cavity and $\beta(t) = \langle b(t) \rangle$ is the mechanical complex amplitude. Moreover, considering $\langle a_{\text{out},f}(t) \rangle = \alpha_{\text{out},f}(t) = \sqrt{2\kappa_1}\alpha(t) - \alpha_{\text{in},f}(t)$, the classical input $\langle a_{\text{in},f}(t) \rangle = \alpha_{\text{in},f}(t)$ in Eq. (8) is given by

$$\alpha_{\text{in},f}(t) = \sqrt{\eta_f(1-T)}\alpha_{\text{in},f}(t-\tau) + \sqrt{\eta_f T}\alpha_{\text{in}}(t-\tau) - \sqrt{2\kappa\eta_c\eta_f(1-T)}\alpha(t-\tau). \quad (10)$$

Ultimately, we are interested in the dynamics of quantum fluctuations around the classical steady state. Therefore, we set the derivatives on the left-hand side of Eqs. (8) and (9) to zero and remove the time dependence of the amplitudes in Eq. (10) in the long-time limit to obtain

$$\alpha_{\text{in},f}^{\text{SS}} = \frac{1}{1 - \sqrt{\eta_f(1-T)}} \left[\sqrt{\eta_f T}\alpha_{\text{in}} - \sqrt{2\kappa\eta_c\eta_f(1-T)}\alpha^{\text{SS}} \right], \quad (11)$$

$$\beta^{\text{SS}} = \frac{ig_0}{i\Omega + \gamma} |\alpha^{\text{SS}}|^2, \quad (12)$$

$$\alpha^{\text{SS}} = \sqrt{2\kappa\eta_c\eta_f T}\alpha_{\text{in}} \left\{ 2\kappa\eta_c\sqrt{\eta_f(1-T)} + (i\Delta_0 + \kappa - 2ig_0\text{Re}[\beta^{\text{SS}}]) \left[1 - \sqrt{\eta_f(1-T)} \right] \right\}^{-1}. \quad (13)$$

From Eq. (12), we can see that the optical field shifts the position of the membrane by an amount dependent on the optomechanical coupling strength, the mechanical resonance frequency, the mechanical damping rate, and the optical intensity. This mechanical shift then alters the cavity detuning through the intracavity intensity given by Eq. (13). Therefore, for a given input laser intensity, the system can exhibit multiple stable states, each characterized by a different value of mechanical displacement. To show this, we plot the normalized steady-state intracavity photon number $|\alpha^{\text{SS}}|^2 / |\alpha_{\text{in}}|^2$ as a function of optical cavity detuning in Fig. 2. As can be seen, the intracavity photon number deviates from its symmetric Lorentzian shape because of the optomechanical interaction. These stable states can be switched between each other by one changing the laser power or frequency of the optical field, which provides a way to control the system's behavior [11–13]. In Fig. 2(a), we can see that by reduction of the

FIG. 2. Steady-state intracavity photon number as a function of optical cavity detuning: (a) for different values of transmittance T of beam splitter BS1, $\eta_f = 1$; (b) for different values of feedback efficiency and fixed transmittance $T = 0.6$. $\kappa/\Omega = 7.14$, $\gamma/\Omega = 10^{-8}$, $g_0/\Omega = 0.003$, and $|\alpha_{\text{in}}|^2 = 8.5 \times 10^6$.

transmittance of the beam splitter, the peak photon number decreases and shifts toward lower detunings. Although we can see bistability in the presence of the feedback loop, this quickly disappears for transmittance T slightly smaller than 1. In Fig. 2(b), for a fixed input laser power and a typical fixed value of transmittance, while bistability exists in the presence of the feedback loop, the peak photon number decreases as we decrease the feedback efficiency η_f . Therefore, the presence of bistability for a system with a feedback loop critically depends on the feedback strength $(1-T)$ and efficiency η_f . Beyond the unwanted bistability, the effect of the coherent feedback loop on this process is a renormalization of the input power, detuning, and optomechanical coupling interaction. We assume monostability in the rest of this paper.

C. Quantum dynamics

For a strong coherent laser drive, the system dynamics can be approximated by a linearized description considering only small fluctuations around the semiclassical steady state given by Eqs. (12) and (13). For linearization, we replace the cavity field with $a(t) \rightarrow a(t) + \alpha^{\text{SS}}$ and $b(t) \rightarrow b(t) + \beta^{\text{SS}}$. The linearized Hamiltonian describing the system is given by [11–13]

$$H/\hbar = \Delta a^\dagger a + \Omega b^\dagger b + g(a^\dagger + a)(b^\dagger + b), \quad (14)$$

where $g = g_0\alpha^{\text{SS}}$ (α^{SS} is generally complex, but this can be resolved by one suitably modifying the phase of the driving laser) denotes the light-enhanced optomechanical coupling in the linearized regime and $\Delta = \Delta_0 + 2g_0\text{Re}[\beta^{\text{SS}}]$ denotes the shifted detuning. Our goal is to study the behavior of the field leaking out of beam splitter BS1. First, we characterize the system dynamics for the intracavity field-membrane subsystem. The system evolution is well described by Heisenberg-Langevin equations for the field

and membrane fluctuations as

$$\dot{a} = -i\Delta a - \kappa a + ig(b + b^\dagger) + \sqrt{2\kappa}a_{\text{in},t}(t), \quad (15)$$

$$\dot{b} = -i\Omega b - \gamma b + ig(a + a^\dagger) + \sqrt{2\gamma}b_{\text{in}}(t). \quad (16)$$

Although we are focusing on the membrane-in-the-middle setup, the linearized equations of motion are general and can be applied to any optomechanical system.

The transmitted output field $a_{\text{out}}(t)$ is related to the input vacuum field and the output of the cavity according to the beam-splitter relation given by

$$a_{\text{out}}(t) = \sqrt{1-T}a_{\text{in}}(t) + \sqrt{T}a_{\text{out},f}(t). \quad (17)$$

Now we are in a position to investigate how the feedback loop can be used to generate squeezing. For a detailed treatment of the procedure and calculations, see the [Appendix](#). We first solve the system dynamics in the frequency space and relate the cavity output field $a_{\text{out},f}$ and input field $a_{\text{in},f}$ via the scattering matrix (denoted by S ; see Fig. 1 and the [Appendix](#)). Then, another scattering matrix, denoted by Z , allows us to relate a_{out} to the system inputs a_{in} , b_{in} , c_{in} , and f_{in} . Finally, the spectrum of the output field or mechanical oscillator can be calculated from the scattering-matrix elements and the correlations of the input fields. The degree of squeezing of the output optical quadrature or mechanical oscillator depends on the phase of the local oscillator, the feedback parameters, detuning, and the optomechanical coupling rate.

The output fields at the detection point can be related to the input fields via elements of the scattering matrix as

$$\begin{aligned} a_{\text{out}}[\omega] &= Z_{11}[\omega]a_{\text{in}}[\omega] + Z_{12}[\omega]a_{\text{in}}^\dagger + Z_{13}[\omega]b_{\text{in}}[\omega] \\ &+ Z_{14}[\omega]b_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega] + Z_{15}[\omega]c_{\text{in}}[\omega] + Z_{16}[\omega]c_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega] \\ &+ Z_{17}[\omega]f_{\text{in}}[\omega] + Z_{18}[\omega]f_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega], \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{aligned} a_{\text{out}}^\dagger[\omega] &= Z_{21}[\omega]a_{\text{in}}[\omega] + Z_{22}[\omega]a_{\text{in}}^\dagger + Z_{23}[\omega]b_{\text{in}}[\omega] \\ &+ Z_{24}[\omega]b_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega] + Z_{25}[\omega]c_{\text{in}}[\omega] + Z_{26}[\omega]c_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega] \\ &+ Z_{27}[\omega]f_{\text{in}}[\omega] + Z_{28}[\omega]f_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega], \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where analytical expressions for Z_{ij} are given in the [Appendix](#).

III. ENHANCED OPTICAL SQUEEZING

We now consider a general quadrature $X_{\text{out}}^\phi[\omega] = [a_{\text{out}}[\omega] \exp(-i\phi) + a_{\text{out}}^\dagger[\omega] \exp(i\phi)]/\sqrt{2}$, where the angle ϕ can be controlled by the phase of the local oscillator. We

then calculate the spectral density of the general quadrature as

$$\delta(\omega + \omega')S_{\text{out}}^\phi(\omega) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \langle X_{\text{out}}^\phi[\omega]X_{\text{out}}^\phi[\omega'] + (\omega \leftrightarrow \omega') \rangle, \quad (20)$$

where the notation $(\omega \leftrightarrow \omega')$ denotes swapping of the arguments of the first term [14]. The noise spectrum of X_{out}^ϕ in terms of amplitude and phase quadratures ($X_{\text{out}} \equiv X_{\text{out}}^{\phi=0}$ and $Y_{\text{out}} \equiv X_{\text{out}}^{\phi=\pi/2}$) is then given by

$$S_{\text{out}}^\phi(\omega) = S_{\text{out}}^{XX}(\omega)\cos^2\phi + S_{\text{out}}^{YY}(\omega)\sin^2\phi + S_{\text{out}}^{XY}(\omega)\sin 2\phi. \quad (21)$$

The three noise spectra, $S_{\text{out}}^{XX}(\omega)$, $S_{\text{out}}^{YY}(\omega)$, and cross-correlation

$$S_{\text{out}}^{XY}(\omega) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \langle X_{\text{out}}[-\omega]Y_{\text{out}}[\omega] + Y_{\text{out}}[-\omega]X_{\text{out}}[\omega] \rangle, \quad (22)$$

fully characterize the proposed optomechanical system as a generator of squeezed light. The expressions for these noise spectra can be calculated from the elements of the scattering matrix and the noise affecting the system. The output quadrature exhibits quantum squeezing when $S_{\text{out}}^\phi(\omega) < 1/2$, i.e., the variance of the generalized quadrature is below the shot-noise level.

The optimal squeezing spectrum can be calculated by one considering a frequency-dependent optimal phase $\phi_{\text{opt}}(\omega)$ possessing the minimum-noise spectrum:

$$S_{\text{out}}^{\text{opt}}(\omega) = \frac{2S_{\text{out}}^{XX}S_{\text{out}}^{YY} - 2(S_{\text{out}}^{XY})^2}{S_{\text{out}}^{XX} + S_{\text{out}}^{YY} + \sqrt{(S_{\text{out}}^{XX} - S_{\text{out}}^{YY})^2 + 4(S_{\text{out}}^{XY})^2}}, \quad (23)$$

$$\phi_{\text{opt}}(\omega) = \frac{1}{2} \arctan \left[\frac{2S_{\text{out}}^{XY}(\omega)}{S_{\text{out}}^{XX}(\omega) - S_{\text{out}}^{YY}(\omega)} \right]. \quad (24)$$

The emergence of noise asymmetry can also be characterized by the noise-asymmetry degree $r(\omega) = S_{\text{out}}^{\text{opt}}(\omega)/S_{\text{out}}^{\text{ant}}(\omega)$, where $S_{\text{out}}^{\text{ant}}(\omega)$ is the noise spectrum of the antisqueezed quadrature with angle $\phi_{\text{opt}} + \pi/2$. The use of Gaussian states in quantum information and measurement systems is challenging due to the unavoidable corruption of pure states by environmental interactions. Consequently, the Gaussian states used in experiments are typically mixed states. We determine their level of purity by [70]

$$\mu(\omega) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{S_{\text{out}}^{XX}(\omega)S_{\text{out}}^{YY}(\omega) - [S_{\text{out}}^{XY}(\omega)]^2}}. \quad (25)$$

It is crucial to examine the variations of the control parameters and investigate the performance of the

FIG. 3. (a) Optimal output quadrature spectrum as a function of transmittance of the coherent beam splitter for three different values of overall efficiency. (b)–(f) Degree of squeezing, purity, optimal frequency, laser detuning, and phase of the squeezing versus transmittance of the coherent beam splitter. $\kappa/\Omega = 7.14$, $\gamma/\Omega = 10^{-8}$, $C_q = 1$, $\bar{n} = 10^6$, and $\Omega\tau = \pi$.

scheme for squeezing generation. These control parameters are the transmittance of the beam splitter, the detection frequency, quantum cooperativity, and the laser detuning. In our calculations, we use experimentally realizable parameters in the unresolved-sideband regime of cavity optomechanics; that is, we consider a high-quality-factor mechanical oscillator $Q_m = \Omega/\gamma = 10^8$ with a frequency $\Omega = 2\pi \times 1.4$ MHz that is much smaller than the cavity damping rate $\kappa = 2\pi \times 10$ MHz. The optimal feedback delay $\Omega\tau = \pi$.

To see how the coherent feedback loop affects the output squeezing, in Fig. 3(a), we show the spectrum of the output quadrature on a logarithmic scale as a function of transmittance of the beam splitter for unit quantum cooperativity, $C_q = C/\bar{n} = g^2/\gamma\kappa\bar{n}$. Here we present squeezing on a decibel scale using the following definition: $-10 \log_{10} S_{\text{out}}^{\phi}(\omega)/S_{\text{shot noise}}$, where $S_{\text{shot noise}} = 1/2$ (0 dB means the shot-noise level). Use of the feedback loop ($T \neq 1$) can lead to significantly more squeezing of the output quadrature. Specifically, we can reach 7.4-, 2.8-, and 1.8-dB increase in squeezing for η values of 0.99, 0.90, and 0.80, respectively, when we use a feedback loop with proper transmittance of the beam splitter. Note that we define the overall detection efficiency as the product of the feedback efficiency and the coupling efficiency $\eta = \eta_c \eta_f$. Optical squeezing is one of the consequences of optomechanical interaction. If we send back a fraction of the squeezed output light from the cavity to the cavity input, the squeezing effect will be enhanced, and we will get more squeezing than in the open-loop case. High reflection gives multiple rounds of squeezing, and losses in the feedback loop increase the optimal transmittance of the beam splitter. It would not be beneficial to send back a

FIG. 4. (a) Optimal output quadrature spectrum as a function of frequency for three different values of overall efficiency. (b)–(f) Degree of squeezing, purity, optimal transmittance, laser detuning, and phase of the squeezing versus frequency. $\kappa/\Omega = 7.14$, $\gamma/\Omega = 10^{-8}$, $C_q = 1$, $\bar{n} = 10^6$, and $\Omega\tau = \pi$.

large fraction of the output if a significant part of it will be lost.

The degree of noise asymmetry, purity, optimal detection frequency, detuning, and phase as a function of the transmittance of the beam splitter corresponding to Fig. 3(a) are plotted in Figs. 3(b)–3(f). We see that the squeezing phase rotates as a function of transmittance, reaching zero at the mechanical resonance and zero detuning for the open-loop case.

In Fig. 4(a), we plot the spectrum of the output quadrature on a logarithmic scale as a function of frequency for unit quantum cooperativity and different values of feedback efficiency. We can see that the generated squeezing is resonantly enhanced close to the mechanical resonance, resulting in significant amounts of squeezing normally existing in only a very small band of frequencies around the center frequency Ω . However, this squeezing bandwidth is increased by the use of a coherent feedback loop. The degree of noise asymmetry, purity, optimal transmittance, detuning, and phase as a function of the transmittance of the beam splitter corresponding to Fig. 4(a) are plotted in Figs. 4(b)–4(f).

In Fig. 5(a), we plot the optimal squeezing as a function of quantum optomechanical cooperativity for different values of the efficiency of the coherent feedback loop. We can see that increasing the optomechanical cooperativity enhances the level of squeezing in the output quadrature and the closed-loop system generates more squeezing with respect to the open-loop system. The degree of noise asymmetry, purity, optimal transmittance, detuning, phase, and frequency as a function of the quantum optomechanical cooperativity corresponding to Fig. 5(a) are shown in Figs. 5(b)–5(g).

FIG. 5. (a) Optimal output quadrature spectrum as a function of quantum cooperativity for three different values of overall efficiency. (b)–(g) Degree of squeezing, purity, transmittance, optimal frequency, laser detuning, and phase versus quantum cooperativity. $\kappa/\Omega = 7.14$, $\gamma/\Omega = 10^{-8}$, $\bar{n} = 10^6$, and $\Omega\tau = \pi$.

In Fig. 6(a), we show the optimal squeezing as a function of normalized laser detuning for a fixed value of quantum optomechanical cooperativity and different values of feedback efficiency. As before, our turning on the feedback loop leads to more squeezing of the output quadrature. The dependence of the squeezing spectrum on the detuning is not the same as in the open-loop case (dashed gray line). The degree of noise asymmetry, purity, optimal transmittance, frequency, and phase as a function of the laser detuning corresponding to Fig. 6(a) are shown in Figs. 6(b)–6(f).

All these results demonstrate that fine-tuning of T , Δ , and ω is crucial as η approaches unity. It allows us to

FIG. 6. (a) Optimal output quadrature spectrum as a function of detuning for three different values of overall efficiency. (b)–(f) Degree of squeezing, purity, transmittance, optimal frequency, and phase of the squeezing versus laser detuning. $\kappa/\Omega = 7.14$, $\gamma/\Omega = 10^{-8}$, $C_q = 1$, $\bar{n} = 10^6$, and $\Omega\tau = \pi$.

reach substantially larger squeezing of more than 9 dB by coherent feedback as compared with 3 dB without feedback.

IV. CONDITIONAL MECHANICAL SQUEEZING

Generation of the squeezed mechanical state conditioned on the measurement result is possible [11,35,71]. For instance, it has been shown that squeezed mechanical states can be generated via single-quadrature detection in the resolved-sideband regime of cavity optomechanics [35,71]. In this section, we numerically show that the generation of unconditional mechanical squeezing for the chosen system parameters (in the unresolved-sideband regime) is impossible. We therefore focus on squeezing generated conditioned on measuring the optical output instead, and show that coherent feedback can improve this conditional squeezing by reducing the thermal noise in the mechanical state.

We can obtain the mechanical operators in terms of input noise in the frequency domain as

$$b[\omega] = Z_{31}[\omega]a_{\text{in}}[\omega] + Z_{32}[\omega]a_{\text{in}}^{\dagger} + Z_{33}[\omega]b_{\text{in}}[\omega] + Z_{34}[\omega]b_{\text{in}}^{\dagger}[\omega] + Z_{35}[\omega]c_{\text{in}}[\omega] + Z_{36}[\omega]c_{\text{in}}^{\dagger}[\omega] + Z_{37}[\omega]f_{\text{in}}[\omega] + Z_{38}[\omega]f_{\text{in}}^{\dagger}[\omega], \quad (26)$$

$$b^{\dagger}[\omega] = Z_{41}[\omega]a_{\text{in}}[\omega] + Z_{42}[\omega]a_{\text{in}}^{\dagger} + Z_{43}[\omega]b_{\text{in}}[\omega] + Z_{44}[\omega]b_{\text{in}}^{\dagger}[\omega] + Z_{45}[\omega]c_{\text{in}}[\omega] + Z_{46}[\omega]c_{\text{in}}^{\dagger}[\omega] + Z_{47}[\omega]f_{\text{in}}[\omega] + Z_{48}[\omega]f_{\text{in}}^{\dagger}[\omega], \quad (27)$$

where analytical expressions for Z_{ij} are given in the Appendix. These equations together with Eqs. (18) and (19) can be used to evaluate the conditional variance of the mechanics by one considering a homodyne measurement in a Gaussian state. Therefore, we define the covariance matrix as

$$\mathbf{V}_{pq}[\omega] = \frac{1}{2} \langle \mathbf{r}_p[\omega]\mathbf{r}_q[-\omega] + \mathbf{r}_q[-\omega]\mathbf{r}_p[\omega] \rangle \quad (28)$$

to extract the quantum correlation between the mechanical and output optical modes, where $\mathbf{r}[\omega] = [X_{\text{out}}[\omega], Y_{\text{out}}[\omega], x[\omega], p[\omega]]^T$. We then write the covariance matrix of the composite system as

$$\mathbf{V} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{C} \\ \mathbf{C}^T & \mathbf{B} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (29)$$

Here, \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , and \mathbf{C} are 2×2 matrices, where \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} account for the properties of optical and mechanical modes, respectively, while \mathbf{C} describes intermode correlations.

We would like to express the conditional state of the mechanical mode upon obtaining a particular measurement

outcome as well as the probability distribution over outcomes in terms of elements of \mathbf{V} . The covariance matrix of mechanics after the measurement is independent of the measurement outcome and is given by [72]

$$\mathbf{B}^c = \mathbf{B} - \mathbf{C}^T(\Pi\mathbf{A}\Pi)^{-1}\mathbf{C}, \quad (30)$$

where

$$\Pi = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (31)$$

and $(\Pi\mathbf{A}\Pi)^{-1}$ denotes the (Moore-Penrose) pseudoinverse. We note that the expression given by Eq. (30) is for an X measurement. A measurement of an arbitrary optical quadrature X^ϕ can be obtained by the replacements

$$\mathbf{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{R}_{-\phi}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{R}_{-\phi}^T, \quad (32)$$

$$\mathbf{C} \rightarrow \mathbf{C}\mathbf{R}_{-\phi}^T, \quad (33)$$

where

$$\mathbf{R}_\phi = \begin{pmatrix} \cos\phi & \sin\phi \\ -\sin\phi & \cos\phi \end{pmatrix}. \quad (34)$$

The final mechanical state will be a Gaussian state with the exact orientation and squeezing determined by the detection and optomechanical cooperativity. Analogously to the optical case, we then define the variance of the general mechanical quadrature

$$\begin{aligned} \langle x_\theta^2[\omega] \rangle &= \mathbf{B}_{11}^c[\omega]\cos^2\theta + \mathbf{B}_{22}^c[\omega]\sin^2\theta \\ &+ \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{B}_{12}^c[\omega] + \mathbf{B}_{21}^c[\omega])\sin 2\theta. \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

The conditional variances of the general mechanical quadrature operator can be evaluated as

$$\langle x_\theta^2 \rangle = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \langle x_\theta^2[\omega] \rangle d\omega. \quad (36)$$

The energy equipartition is not valid anymore since $\langle x_0^2 \rangle \neq \langle x_{\pi/2}^2 \rangle$, which means the steady state of the system is not a thermal-equilibrium state. The mean energy of the mechanical oscillator in the steady state can be written as

$$U = \frac{\Omega}{2} (\langle x_0^2 \rangle + \langle x_{\pi/2}^2 \rangle) = \Omega \left(n_{\text{eff}} + \frac{1}{2} \right). \quad (37)$$

To obtain the unconditional expression, one just needs to replace \mathbf{B}_{ij}^c with \mathbf{B}_{ij} in Eq. (36). In the case where $n_{\text{eff}} < 1$, the ground state can be approached. Note that we consider the mechanical variance in decibels as $-10 \log_{10}[2\langle x_\theta^2 \rangle]$.

We study the conditional and unconditional mechanical squeezing numerically in Fig. 7, which shows the

FIG. 7. (a) Conditional (solid lines) and unconditional (dashed lines) variance of general mechanical quadrature x_θ as a function of transmittance for three different values of overall efficiency. (b)–(g) Degree of noise asymmetry, purity, effective phonon number, optimal detuning, optimal homodyne-detection phase, and phase of general mechanical quadrature versus transmittance. $\kappa/\Omega = 7.14$, $\gamma/\Omega = 10^{-8}$, $C_q = 1$, $\bar{n} = 10^6$, and optimal feedback delay $\Omega\tau = 1.46$.

mechanical squeezing as a function of transmittance for three different efficiency values. It reveals that the effect of the feedback loop on mechanical squeezing is nuanced and depends on both the measurement conditions and the loop efficiency. In the unconditional case (dashed lines), while the feedback loop can reduce the overall noise level, it does not produce mechanical squeezing for the parameters considered. This is consistent with our open-loop findings, where squeezing cannot be achieved without conditioning on the measurement. For the conditional case (shown by solid lines), we observe that mechanical squeezing can be achieved, particularly for high-efficiency feedback loops. With a nearly perfect feedback loop ($\eta_f > 0.99$), the squeezing surpasses that of the open-loop case. However, for more-realistic feedback loops with lower efficiencies ($\eta_f < 0.91$), the enhancement diminishes, and the open-loop squeezing is greater than in the closed-loop case. Interestingly, our results demonstrate that feedback-enhanced squeezing is more robust regarding inefficiencies than the open-loop scenario. Specifically, while mechanical squeezing in the open-loop case is lost for $\eta_c = 0.975$, it can still be achieved with a feedback loop for efficiencies $\eta = \eta_f\eta_c$ down to 0.90. As $T \rightarrow 0$, the conditional and unconditional variances converge. In this limit, the measurement part becomes decoupled from the cavity, leaving only the noise from the feedback loop and the second mirror coupled to the cavity. Note that we consider a fixed value of quantum cooperativity $C_q = 1$ throughout our analysis. We observe a transition in the mechanical variance near $T \approx 1$ when closing the loop. This transition is related to a stability change in the system, occurring at a

specific transmittance T of 0.994 (see the Appendix for stability diagrams).

Figures 7(b)–7(d) illustrate additional system characteristics as a function of the transmittance of the beam splitter, including the degree of noise asymmetry, purity, effective phonon number, detuning, and optimal homodyne-detection phase. In the unconditional scenario, the squeezing remains unaffected by the transmittance T . However, in the conditional scenario, it is reduced compared with the open-loop case and varies with T . Finally, we note that the use of a feedback loop with appropriate delay and transmittance can facilitate ground-state cooling [see Fig. 7(d)]. Conditioning allows improved cooling and squeezing of the mechanical oscillator. To obtain the minimum conditional variance on mechanical resonance $\langle x_\theta^2[\omega = \Omega] \rangle$, we optimize both the phase of the general mechanical quadrature and the homodyne-detection angle.

The conditional mechanical squeezing and the unconditional mechanical squeezing for various overall efficiencies are shown in Fig. 8(a). We can see that for increasing quantum cooperativity, the conditional mechanical squeezing first tends to increase and then to decrease. The degree of noise asymmetry, purity, effective phonon number, optimal transmittance, detuning, homodyne-detection phase, and squeezing angle are plotted versus quantum cooperativity in Figs. 8(b)–8(g), respectively.

In Fig. 9(a), we show how the conditional mechanical squeezing and the unconditional mechanical squeezing

FIG. 8. (a) Conditional (solid lines) and unconditional (dashed lines) variance of general mechanical quadrature x_θ as a function of quantum cooperativity for three different values of overall efficiency. (b)–(g) Degree of noise asymmetry, purity, effective phonon number, optimal transmittance, detuning, phase of the homodyne detection, and phase of general mechanical quadrature versus quantum cooperativity. $\kappa/\Omega = 7.14$, $\gamma/\Omega = 10^{-8}$, $\bar{n} = 10^6$, and optimal feedback delay $\Omega\tau = 1.46$.

FIG. 9. (a) Conditional (solid lines) and unconditional (dashed lines) mechanical squeezing as a function of laser detuning for three different values of overall efficiency. (b)–(g) Degree of noise asymmetry, purity, effective phonon number, optimal transmittance, phase of the homodyne detection, and phase of general mechanical quadrature versus laser detuning. $\kappa/\Omega = 7.14$, $\gamma/\Omega = 10^{-8}$, $C_q = 1$, $\bar{n} = 10^6$, and $\Omega\tau = 1.46$.

vary as a function of the detuning. Similarly to what occurred for optical squeezing, our changing the laser detuning has a significant effect on the conditional mechanical squeezing. The degree of noise asymmetry, purity, effective phonon number, optimal transmittance, optimal homodyne-detection phase, and squeezing angle are plotted versus the normalized detuning in Figs. 9(b)–9(g), respectively.

V. CONCLUSION

We have proposed a scheme for generating enhanced squeezing in the output spectrum of light and the mechanical mode in the optomechanical setup subjected to a coherent quantum feedback in the unresolved-sideband regime [67,68]. In particular, we have shown that if the effective quantum cooperativity $C_q \sim 1$, then an appreciable amount of squeezing can be obtained in the output light at high temperatures. Moreover, we have shown that it is possible to generate mechanical squeezing conditioned on the measurement results of the output light in a system subjected to a coherent feedback loop, although without the measurement this is not possible. Our study also showed that coherent feedback can substantially enhance already existing mechanical squeezing. The results showed that feedback can provide enhancement of mechanical squeezing compared with the open-loop case without feedback. Naturally, this enhancement is sensitive to the efficiency of the feedback loop. However, with a nearly perfect feedback loop ($\eta_f > 0.99$), the squeezing was increased over the open-loop case. But with realistic feedback loops that in essence possess inefficiency ($\eta_f < 0.91$), the enhancement diminished and the open-loop squeezing was greater than in the closed-loop case. These findings indicate that while

coherent feedback has the potential to enhance squeezing, high efficiency of the feedback system needs to be reached. Further technical work in experiments is needed to increase feedback efficiency before it can provide substantial benefits for mechanical squeezing. The scheme presents an alternative approach to generate quantum squeezing with current experimental technologies [47–49], which can play an important role in ultrahigh-precision measurements [42–44] and related fields. Our study was conducted with dimensionless variables, enabling its translation to any optomechanical system capable of operating in the unresolved-sideband regime. For instance, the membrane-in-the-middle setup [48] and levitated nanoparticles [73–75] are promising candidates for practical implementation.

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APPENDIX: METHODS

In this appendix, we present the full system dynamics in matrix form. We define the vector of fields $\mathbf{u}(t) = [a(t), a^\dagger(t), b(t), b^\dagger(t)]^T$, the corresponding vector of input noise to the system

$$\mathbf{u}_{\text{in}}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{\eta_c} a_{\text{in},f}(t) \\ \sqrt{\eta_c} a_{\text{in},f}^\dagger(t) \\ b_{\text{in}}(t) \\ b_{\text{in}}^\dagger(t) \end{bmatrix} + \sqrt{1 - \eta_c} \begin{bmatrix} f_{\text{in}}(t) \\ f_{\text{in}}^\dagger(t) \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A1})$$

and the matrix $\mathbf{H} = \text{diag}[\sqrt{2\kappa}, \sqrt{2\kappa}, \sqrt{2\gamma}, \sqrt{2\gamma}]$ to rewrite the equations of motion for the optical and mechanical fields as

$$\frac{d}{dt} \mathbf{u}(t) = \mathbf{D} \mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{H} \mathbf{u}_{\text{in}}(t), \quad (\text{A2})$$

where the drift matrix is given by

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{pmatrix} -\kappa - i\Delta & 0 & ig & ig \\ 0 & -\kappa + i\Delta & -ig & -ig \\ ig & ig & -\gamma - i\Omega & 0 \\ -ig & -ig & 0 & -\gamma + i\Omega \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{A3})$$

We transform Eq. (A2) in the frequency domain by taking the Fourier transform of all the operators and noise sources defined via $o[\omega] = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dt e^{i\omega t} o(t)$. We then use the input-output relation $a_{\text{out},f}[\omega] = \sqrt{\kappa} a[\omega] - a_{\text{in},f}[\omega]$ to relate output and input fields. Therefore, the equations of motion in the frequency domain become

$$\mathbf{u}[\omega] = -(\mathbf{D} + i\omega \mathbf{I}_{4 \times 4})^{-1} \mathbf{H} \mathbf{u}_{\text{in}}[\omega], \quad (\text{A4})$$

with $\mathbf{I}_{4 \times 4}$ being the identity matrix. By our defining the output vector of noise $\mathbf{u}_{\text{out}}[\omega] = [a_{\text{out},f}[\omega], a_{\text{out},f}^\dagger[\omega], b_{\text{out}}[\omega], b_{\text{out}}^\dagger[\omega]]^T$, the input-output relation $\mathbf{u}_{\text{out}}[\omega] = \mathbf{G} \mathbf{u}[\omega] - \mathbf{u}_{\text{in}}[\omega]$ relates output and input fields with the diagonal matrix $\mathbf{G} = \text{diag}[\sqrt{2\kappa_1}, \sqrt{2\kappa_1}, \sqrt{2\gamma}, \sqrt{2\gamma}]$. By using Eq. (A4), we then obtain the fluctuations of the output fields as

$$\mathbf{u}_{\text{out}}[\omega] = \mathbf{S}[\omega] \mathbf{u}_{\text{in}}[\omega], \quad (\text{A5})$$

where we have introduced the scattering matrix $\mathbf{S}[\omega]$ that relates the input fields to the transmitted fields. Therefore, we can write

$$\begin{aligned} a_{\text{out},f}[\omega] &= \sqrt{\eta_c} S_{11}[\omega] a_{\text{in},f}[\omega] + \sqrt{\eta_c} S_{12}[\omega] a_{\text{in},f}^\dagger[\omega] \\ &\quad + \sqrt{1 - \eta_c} S_{11}[\omega] f_{\text{in}}[\omega] + \sqrt{1 - \eta_c} S_{12}[\omega] f_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega] \\ &\quad + S_{13}[\omega] b_{\text{in}}[\omega] + S_{14}[\omega] b_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega], \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A6})$$

$$\begin{aligned} a_{\text{out},f}^\dagger[\omega] &= \sqrt{\eta_c} S_{21}[\omega] a_{\text{in},f}[\omega] + \sqrt{\eta_c} S_{22}[\omega] a_{\text{in},f}^\dagger[\omega] \\ &\quad + \sqrt{1 - \eta_c} S_{21}[\omega] f_{\text{in}}[\omega] + \sqrt{1 - \eta_c} S_{22}[\omega] f_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega] \\ &\quad + S_{23}[\omega] b_{\text{in}}[\omega] + S_{24}[\omega] b_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega], \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A7})$$

$$\begin{aligned} b_{\text{out}}[\omega] &= \sqrt{\eta_c} S_{31}[\omega] a_{\text{in},f}[\omega] + \sqrt{\eta_c} S_{32}[\omega] a_{\text{in},f}^\dagger[\omega] \\ &\quad + \sqrt{1 - \eta_c} S_{31}[\omega] f_{\text{in}}[\omega] + \sqrt{1 - \eta_c} S_{32}[\omega] f_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega] \\ &\quad + S_{33}[\omega] b_{\text{in}}[\omega] + S_{34}[\omega] b_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega], \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A8})$$

$$\begin{aligned} b_{\text{out}}^\dagger[\omega] &= \sqrt{\eta_c} S_{41}[\omega] a_{\text{in},f}[\omega] + \sqrt{\eta_c} S_{42}[\omega] a_{\text{in},f}^\dagger[\omega] \\ &\quad + \sqrt{1 - \eta_c} S_{41}[\omega] f_{\text{in}}[\omega] + \sqrt{1 - \eta_c} S_{42}[\omega] f_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega] \\ &\quad + S_{43}[\omega] b_{\text{in}}[\omega] + S_{44}[\omega] b_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega], \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A9})$$

where the S_{ij} are elements of the scattering matrix that relates the cavity output to the input fields. We then introduce the susceptibilities of the optical field and the mechanical oscillator as

$$\chi_c^{-1}[\omega] = -i\Delta - \kappa + i\omega, \quad (\text{A10})$$

$$\chi_m^{-1}[\omega] = -i\Omega - \gamma + i\omega, \quad (\text{A11})$$

and

$$\Xi[\omega] = [g^2 (\chi_c[\omega] - \chi_c^*[\omega]) (\chi_m[\omega] - \chi_m^*[\omega]) + 1]^{-1}. \quad (\text{A12})$$

Hereafter, the frequency dependence of the functions is implicit for conciseness of notation. The relevant scattering-matrix elements S_{ij} are as follows:

$$S_{11} = 2\sqrt{\eta_c\kappa}\chi_c [g^2\chi_c^*(\chi_m - \chi_m^*) - 1] \Xi - 1, \quad (\text{A13a})$$

$$S_{12} = 2\sqrt{\eta_c\kappa}g^2\chi_c\chi_c^*(\chi_m - \chi_m^*) \Xi, \quad (\text{A13b})$$

$$S_{13} = 2ig\sqrt{\eta_c\gamma\kappa}\chi_c\chi_m\Xi, \quad (\text{A13c})$$

$$S_{14} = 2ig\sqrt{\eta_c\gamma\kappa}\chi_c\chi_m^*\Xi, \quad (\text{A13d})$$

$$S_{21} = 2\sqrt{\eta_c\kappa}g^2\chi_c\chi_c^*(\chi_m - \chi_m^*) \Xi, \quad (\text{A13e})$$

$$S_{22} = 2\sqrt{\eta_c\kappa}\chi_c^* [g^2\chi_c(\chi_m^* - \chi_m) - 1] \Xi - 1, \quad (\text{A13f})$$

$$S_{23} = -2ig\sqrt{\eta_c\gamma\kappa}\chi_c^*\chi_m\Xi, \quad (\text{A13g})$$

$$S_{24} = -2ig\sqrt{\eta_c\gamma\kappa}\chi_c^*\chi_m^*\Xi, \quad (\text{A13h})$$

$$S_{31} = 2ig\sqrt{\gamma\kappa}\chi_c\chi_m\Xi, \quad (\text{A13i})$$

$$S_{32} = 2ig\sqrt{\gamma\kappa}\chi_c^*\chi_m\Xi, \quad (\text{A13j})$$

$$S_{33} = -1 - 2\gamma\chi_m(1 - g^2(\chi_c - \chi_c^*)\chi_m^*) \Xi, \quad (\text{A13k})$$

$$S_{34} = 2g^2\gamma(\chi_c - \chi_c^*)\chi_m\chi_m^*\Xi, \quad (\text{A13l})$$

$$S_{41} = -2ig\sqrt{\gamma\kappa}\chi_c\chi_m^*\Xi, \quad (\text{A13m})$$

$$S_{42} = -2ig\sqrt{\gamma\kappa}\chi_c^*\chi_m^*\Xi, \quad (\text{A13n})$$

$$S_{43} = -2g^2\gamma(\chi_c - \chi_c^*)\chi_m\chi_m^*\Xi, \quad (\text{A13o})$$

$$S_{44} = -1 - 2\gamma(1 + g^2(\chi_c - \chi_c^*)\chi_m)\chi_m^*\Xi. \quad (\text{A13p})$$

We write Eq. (17) in the frequency domain as

$$a_{\text{in},f}[\omega] = \sqrt{\eta_f} \left[\sqrt{T}a_{\text{in}}[\omega]e^{i\omega\tau} - \sqrt{1-T}a_{\text{out},f}[\omega] \right] + \sqrt{1-\eta_f}c_{\text{in},f}[\omega], \quad (\text{A14})$$

$$a_{\text{out}}[\omega] = \sqrt{1-T}a_{\text{in}}[\omega] + \sqrt{T}a_{\text{out},f}[\omega] \quad (\text{A15})$$

to obtain expressions for the output field at the detection point in terms of system input according to Eqs. (18) and (19). We find the following expressions for the coefficients:

$$Z_{11} = \left[e^{i\tau\omega}\sqrt{\eta}(S_{11} + S_{22} - TS_{22}) - \eta\sqrt{(1-T)}e^{2i\tau\omega}(S_{12}S_{21} - S_{11}S_{22}) + \sqrt{1-T} \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A16})$$

$$Z_{12} = \sqrt{\eta}Te^{i\tau\omega}S_{12}\Sigma, \quad (\text{A17})$$

$$Z_{13} = \sqrt{T} \left[e^{i\tau\omega}\sqrt{\eta(1-T)}(S_{22}S_{13} - S_{12}S_{23}) + S_{13} \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A18})$$

$$Z_{14} = \sqrt{T} \left[e^{i\tau\omega}\sqrt{\eta(1-T)}(S_{22}S_{14} - S_{12}S_{24}) + S_{14} \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A19})$$

$$Z_{15} = -\sqrt{T(1-\eta_f)}\eta_c \left[S_{11} - e^{i\tau\omega}\sqrt{(1-T)}\eta(S_{12}S_{21} - S_{11}S_{22}) \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A20})$$

$$Z_{16} = -\sqrt{T(1-\eta_f)}\eta_c S_{12}\Sigma, \quad (\text{A21})$$

$$Z_{17} = \sqrt{T(1 - \eta_c)} \left[S_{11} - e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{(1 - T)\eta} (S_{12}S_{21} - S_{11}S_{22}) \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A22})$$

$$Z_{18} = \sqrt{T(1 - \eta_c)} S_{12} \Sigma, \quad (\text{A23})$$

$$Z_{21} = \sqrt{\eta} T e^{i\tau\omega} S_{21} \Sigma, \quad (\text{A24})$$

$$Z_{22} = \left[\sqrt{\eta} e^{i\tau\omega} (S_{11} + S_{22} - TS_{11}) - \eta \sqrt{(1 - T)} e^{2i\tau\omega} (S_{12}S_{21} - S_{11}S_{22}) + \sqrt{1 - T} \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A25})$$

$$Z_{23} = \sqrt{T} \left[e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\eta(1 - T)} (S_{11}S_{23} - S_{13}S_{21}) + S_{23} \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A26})$$

$$Z_{24} = \sqrt{T} \left[e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\eta(1 - T)} (S_{11}S_{24} - S_{14}S_{21}) + S_{24} \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A27})$$

$$Z_{25} = -\sqrt{T(1 - \eta_f)\eta_c} S_{21} \Sigma, \quad (\text{A28})$$

$$Z_{26} = -\sqrt{T(1 - \eta_f)\eta_c} \left[S_{22} + e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\eta(1 - T)} (S_{11}S_{22} - S_{12}S_{21}) \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A29})$$

$$Z_{27} = \sqrt{T(1 - \eta_c)} S_{21} \Sigma, \quad (\text{A30})$$

$$Z_{28} = \sqrt{T(1 - \eta_c)} \left[S_{22} + e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\eta(1 - T)} (S_{11}S_{22} - S_{12}S_{21}) \right], \quad (\text{A31})$$

$$Z_{31} = e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\frac{\eta T}{2\gamma}} \left[e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\eta(1 - T)} (S_{22}S_{31} - S_{21}S_{32}) + S_{31} \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A32})$$

$$Z_{32} = e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\frac{\eta T}{2\gamma}} \left[e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\eta(1 - T)} (S_{11}S_{32} - S_{12}S_{31}) + S_{32} \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A33})$$

$$\begin{aligned} Z_{33} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\gamma}} \left\{ S_{33} + e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\eta(1 - T)} [(S_{11} + S_{22}) S_{33} - S_{13}S_{31} - S_{23}S_{32}] \right. \\ \left. - e^{2i\tau\omega} (1 - T) \eta [(S_{13}S_{22} - S_{12}S_{23}) S_{31} + (S_{11}S_{23} - S_{13}S_{21}) S_{32}] \right. \\ \left. - e^{2i\tau\omega} (1 - T) \eta [(S_{12}S_{21} - S_{11}S_{22}) S_{33}] + \Sigma^{-1} \right\} \Sigma, \quad (\text{A34}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} Z_{34} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\gamma}} \left\{ S_{34} + e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\eta(1 - T)} [(S_{11} + S_{22}) S_{34} - S_{14}S_{31} - S_{24}S_{32}] \right. \\ \left. - e^{2i\tau\omega} (1 - T) \eta [(S_{14}S_{22} - S_{12}S_{24}) S_{31} + (S_{11}S_{24} - S_{14}S_{21}) S_{32}] \right. \\ \left. - e^{2i\tau\omega} (1 - T) \eta [(S_{12}S_{21} - S_{11}S_{22}) S_{34}] \right\} \Sigma, \quad (\text{A35}) \end{aligned}$$

$$Z_{35} = -\sqrt{\frac{\eta_c(1-\eta_f)}{2\gamma}} \left[S_{31} + e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\eta(1-T)} (S_{22}S_{31} - e^{i\tau\omega} S_{21}S_{32}) \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A36})$$

$$Z_{36} = -\sqrt{\frac{\eta_c(1-\eta_f)}{2\gamma}} \left[S_{32} + e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\eta(1-T)} (S_{11}S_{32} - e^{i\tau\omega} S_{12}S_{31}) \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A37})$$

$$Z_{37} = \sqrt{\frac{1-\eta_c}{2\gamma}} \left[S_{31} + \sqrt{\eta(1-T)} e^{i\omega\tau} (S_{22}S_{31} - S_{21}S_{32}) \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A38})$$

$$Z_{38} = \sqrt{\frac{1-\eta_c}{2\gamma}} \left[S_{32} + \sqrt{\eta(1-T)} e^{i\omega\tau} (S_{11}S_{32} - S_{12}S_{31}) \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A39})$$

$$Z_{41} = e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\frac{\eta T}{2\gamma}} \left[e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\eta(1-T)} (S_{22}S_{41} - S_{21}S_{42}) + S_{41} \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A40})$$

$$Z_{42} = e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\frac{\eta T}{2\gamma}} \left[e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\eta(1-T)} (S_{11}S_{42} - S_{12}S_{41}) + S_{42} \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A41})$$

$$\begin{aligned} Z_{43} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\gamma}} \left\{ S_{34} + e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\eta(1-T)} [(S_{11} + S_{22}) S_{34} - S_{13}S_{41} - S_{23}S_{42}] \right. \\ \left. - e^{2i\tau\omega} (1-T) \eta [(S_{41}S_{22} - S_{21}S_{42}) S_{13} + (S_{11}S_{42} - S_{41}S_{12}) S_{23}] \right. \\ \left. - e^{2i\tau\omega} (1-T) \eta [(S_{12}S_{21} - S_{11}S_{22}) S_{43}] \right\} \Sigma, \quad (\text{A42}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} Z_{44} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\gamma}} \left\{ S_{44} + e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\eta(1-T)} [(S_{11} + S_{22}) S_{44} - S_{14}S_{41} - S_{24}S_{42}] \right. \\ \left. - e^{2i\tau\omega} (1-T) \eta [(S_{14}S_{22} - S_{12}S_{24}) S_{41} + (S_{11}S_{24} - S_{14}S_{21}) S_{42}] \right. \\ \left. - e^{2i\tau\omega} (1-T) \eta [(S_{12}S_{21} - S_{11}S_{22}) S_{44}] + \Sigma^{-1} \right\} \Sigma, \quad (\text{A43}) \end{aligned}$$

$$Z_{45} = -\sqrt{\frac{\eta_c(1-\eta_f)}{2\gamma}} \left[e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\eta(1-T)} (S_{22}S_{41} - S_{21}S_{42}) + S_{41} \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A44})$$

$$Z_{46} = -\sqrt{\frac{\eta_c(1-\eta_f)}{2\gamma}} \left[e^{i\tau\omega} \sqrt{\eta(1-T)} (S_{11}S_{42} - S_{12}S_{41}) + S_{42} \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A45})$$

$$Z_{47} = \sqrt{\frac{1-\eta_c}{2\gamma}} \left[S_{41} + \sqrt{\eta(1-T)} e^{i\omega\tau} (S_{22}S_{41} - S_{21}S_{42}) \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A46})$$

FIG. 10. Region of stability as a function of the optomechanical cooperativity and laser detuning. The white and gray areas correspond to the stable and unstable regimes, respectively. (a) Closed loop with $\Omega\tau = 1.46$ and $T = 0.2$, (b) closed loop with $\Omega\tau = 1.46$ and critical value of $T = 0.994$, (c) open loop with $T = 1$, and (d) closed loop with $\Omega\tau = \pi$ and $T = 0.2$. $\kappa/\Omega = 7.14$, $\gamma/\Omega = 10^{-8}$, and $\eta = 0.8$.

$$Z_{48} = \sqrt{\frac{1 - \eta_c}{2\gamma}} \left[S_{42} + \sqrt{\eta(1 - T)} e^{i\omega\tau} (S_{11}S_{42} - S_{12}S_{41}) \right] \Sigma, \quad (\text{A47})$$

with

$$\Sigma = \left[1 - e^{2i\omega\tau} \eta(1 - T) (S_{12}S_{21} - S_{11}S_{22}) + e^{i\omega\tau} \sqrt{\eta(1 - T)} (S_{11} + S_{22}) \right]^{-1}. \quad (\text{A48})$$

From the above equations, we can see that the output at the detection point (determined by Z_{1j} and Z_{2j}) and the mechanical state (determined by Z_{3j} and Z_{4j}) depend on the phase of the local oscillator, the transmittance of the coherent beam splitter, and the optomechanical coupling strength. For example, in the case of a high-transmittance coherent beam splitter $T = 1$, $Z_{ij} = S_{ij}$ as one should expect, i.e., there is no feedback loop in the system. However, in another limiting case, $T = 0$, $Z_{11} = Z_{22} = 1$ and all other Z_{ij} are zero, which indicates that the beam splitter reflects the input laser and the optomechanical system is disconnected from the other parts of the system. In the case where there is no loss due to the feedback loop $\eta_f = 1$, the coefficients $Z_{i,5}$ and $Z_{i,6}$ with $i = 1, \dots, 4$ become zero. Similarly, in the case where there is no internal loss $\eta_c = 1$, the coefficients $Z_{i,7}$ and $Z_{i,8}$ with $i = 1, \dots, 4$ become zero.

Here we use Eqs. (A16)–(A29) and transformed correlations given by

$$\langle a_{\text{in}}[\omega], a_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega'] \rangle = 2\pi\delta(\omega + \omega'), \quad (\text{A49a})$$

$$\langle a_{\text{in}}[\omega] a_{\text{in}}[\omega']^\dagger \rangle = 2\pi\delta(\omega + \omega'), \quad (\text{A49b})$$

$$\langle b_{\text{in}}[\omega] b_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega'] \rangle = 2\pi(1 + \bar{n})\delta(\omega + \omega'), \quad (\text{A49c})$$

$$\langle b_{\text{in}}[\omega], b_{\text{in}}^\dagger[\omega'] \rangle = 2\pi\delta(\omega + \omega') \quad (\text{A49d})$$

to calculate the spectrum of the output field. The operators $f_{\text{in}}[\omega]$ and $c_{\text{in}}[\omega]$ obey the same correlations as $a_{\text{in}}[\omega]$.

We determine the dynamical stability of the system from the poles of $\Sigma[\omega]$. A stable system requires that the poles lie in the lower half-plane. In Fig. 10, we show the regions of stability versus the optomechanical cooperativity and laser detuning for the case without a coherent feedback loop and for two different feedback delay times. We can see that the stability of the system highly depends on the feedback delay time. Comparing Figs. 10(a)–10(c), one can see the transition of the stability in the system.

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